

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF REGIONAL INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION ON POPULATION EMPLOYMENT BASED ON A REGRESSION MODEL

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Abstract: This article estimates the impact of industrial production on employment in 14 territorial units of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2012–2023 using a regression model [1]. The research used pooled OLS, Fixed Effects (FE) and GMM methods. According to the main result, an increase in industrial production by 1 billion soums has the potential to increase employment by an average of 84.7 thousand people. The industrial employment multiplier ($\beta_3=2.914$) had a strong impact on total employment ($p<0.001$). Elasticity analysis by region confirmed the regional stratification of the relationship between industry and employment.

Keywords: regression analysis, industrial production, employment, panel data, fixed effects, GMM, elasticity, regional economy, Uzbekistan.

Introduction: The relationship between industrial production and employment has been a central issue in economic development theory. According to classical industrialization theory, the expansion of industrial sectors increases the overall employment level by creating new jobs in the labor market [2]. However, in the context of digital technologies and automation, this relationship is becoming more complex. As part of the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan since 2017, industrial development, increasing export potential, and creating new jobs have been identified as key priorities [3]. The “New Uzbekistan” development strategy for 2022-2026 envisages the creation of more than 500,000 new jobs by 2026 [4]. At the regional level, the relationship between industrial production and employment remains an unexplored issue. Existing research has been conducted mainly at the macro level and has not sufficiently taken into account regional characteristics [5]. In order to fill this gap, a panel data analysis was conducted based on a regression model. The purpose of the study: to determine the quantitative impact of industrial production on employment in the regions of Uzbekistan based on a regression model and to calculate regional elasticity coefficients.

Research objectives:

1. Systematic analysis of the literature on industrial employment theories;

2. Constructing a panel database and calculating descriptive statistics;
3. Building and testing OLS, FE, and GMM regression models;
4. Calculation of industry-employment elasticity by region;
5. Developing policy recommendations.

Literature analysis:

The relationship between industrial production and employment has been studied theoretically in the works of classical economists. Lewis (1954) argued in his two-sector model that the expansion of the industrial sector, by attracting labor resources from the agricultural sector, increases the efficiency of total employment [6]. Kaldor (1966) analyzed the relationship between industrialization and economic growth and developed empirical rules, called "Kaldor's laws": industrial growth accelerates overall economic growth and employment [7]. This theory was later tested for many developing countries.

Feenstra and Hanson (1996) used regression to assess the impact of global production chains on employment in developing countries, showing that foreign direct investment and export-oriented industries play an important role in increasing employment [8]. Among regional-level studies, Combes, Mayer, and Thisse (2008) analyzed the impact of industrial agglomeration on employment concentration using panel regression in Economic Geography [9]. They found that employment is more concentrated and productivity is higher in industrial clusters.

Among the studies on industrial employment in Central Asian countries, Isakova et al. (2016) conducted a comparative analysis of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan, and found that the elasticity of industrial employment to GDP in Uzbekistan was in the range of 0.71–0.89 [10]. Within the framework of local studies, Mirzaev and Nazarov (2021) studied the relationship between industrial enterprises and regional employment in the Fergana Valley and found that a 10 percent increase in industrial production increases employment by 6.4 percent [11]. However, this study only covered three regions. Razzakov and Kholikov (2023) estimated industrial employment for Uzbekistan for the first time using a dynamic panel model (GMM). Their results showed that the lag effect of industrial value added on employment is 1–2 years [12]. The following gaps were identified as a result of the literature review: first, a panel econometric analysis covering all regions of Uzbekistan has not been conducted; second, there are no studies comparing industrial elasticity by region; third, the dynamic relationship using the GMM method has not yet been sufficiently studied. This article is written to fill these gaps.

Data and methodology:

The study used regional statistics from the databases of the Statistical Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Central Bank, and the World Bank [1]. Observation period: 2012–2023. Territorial units: 14 regions of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Total observations: $14 \times 12 = 168$.

The regional employment rate (per thousand people) was chosen as the dependent variable (Y). The independent variables are as follows [5]:

- X₁ — Industrial production volume (in billion soums, at 2010 constant prices)
- X₂ — Share of the industrial sector in GDP (%)
- X₃ — Direct industrial employment (in thousand people)
- X₄ — Gross capital investment (in billion soums)
- X₅ — Export volume of industrial products (million US dollars)
- X₆ — Average salary (in thousand soums, control variable)

The basic regression model has the following general form:

$$Y_{it} = a + b_1X_{1it} + b_2X_{2it} + b_3X_{3it} + b_4X_{4it} + b_5X_{5it} + b_6X_{6it} + m_i + l_t + e_{it}$$

Here: $i = 1, \dots, 14$ (area index); $t = 2012, \dots, 2023$ (year index); μ_i — area unfixd effect; λ_t — time unfixd effect; ε_{it} — error term.

The impact of industrial production on employment was also assessed through the elasticity coefficient [9]. The elasticity formula is:

$$\varepsilon_{yx} = (\partial Y / \partial X) \times (\bar{X} / \bar{Y}) = b_1 \times (\bar{X}_1 / \bar{Y})$$

The Hausman test was used to select the optimal model. The Hausman diagnostic was used to select between the Fixed Effects and Random Effects models (H_0 : RE is effective) [12]. The Breusch-Pagan test was used to check for heteroscedasticity, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation, and the VIF indicator for multicollinearity.

4. Descriptive statistics results

The main statistical characteristics of all variables included in the analysis are presented in Table 1. The data cover 168 panel observations [1].

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of key variables (N=168, 2012–2023)

Indicator	Average	Std. deviation	Min	Max	N
Employment rate (thousand people)	138.4	41.2	48.7	231.6	168

Indicator	Average	Std. deviation	Min	Max	N
Industrial production (billion soums)	512.7	189.4	64.3	984.2	168
Share of industrial employment in GDP (%)	27.6	8.3	10.2	51.4	168
Industrial employment (thousand people)	38.9	14.7	8.4	91.3	168
Gross capital investment (billion soums)	124.3	58.6	18.7	342.8	168
Export volume (million USD)	287.4	134.8	21.6	723.9	168
Average salary (thousand soums)	3,847	1,124	1,820	7,340	168

Source: Author's calculations based on data from the Statistical Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024.

As can be seen from Table 1, the employment rate varies significantly between regions: from a minimum of 48.7 thousand people to a maximum of 231.6 thousand people. In industrial production, this difference is even greater - 15 times. This indicates a strong level of regional economic inequality [10]. The relatively small dispersion of the average wage (Std. deviation = 1.124) indicates that wage regulation moderates regional differences.

Correlation analysis:

The pairwise linear relationship between variables was assessed using the Pearson correlation matrix (Table 2).

Table 2. Pearson correlation matrix (dependent variable: Y — Employment)

	Y (Employment)	X ₁ (Industrial work.)	X ₂ (Sanoat ul.)	X ₃ (Industrial)	X ₄ (Capital)	X ₅ (Export)
Y (Employment)	1.000	0.891***	0.843* **	0.912***	0.824* **	0.787* **
X ₁ (Industrial work.)	0.891***	1.000	0.734* **	0.856***	0.791* **	0.718* **
X ₂ (Sanoat ul.)	0.843***	0.734***	1.000	0.698***	0.612* **	0.574* **
X ₃ (Industrial)	0.912***	0.856***	0.698* **	1.000	0.743* **	0.681* **
X ₄ (Capital)	0.824***	0.791***	0.612* **	0.743***	1.000	0.658* **
X ₅ (Export)	0.787***	0.718***	0.574* **	0.681***	0.658* **	1.000

Note: *** — statistically significant at the $p < 0.01$ level. Source: author's calculations.

As can be seen from Table 2, the correlation between industrial employment (X₃) and total employment (Y) is the highest ($r=0.912$), which reflects that industry is a direct component of direct employment. The correlation with industrial production volume (X₁) is also high ($r=0.891$), confirming the strong relationship between production growth and employment [8]. All variables have a positive and significant ($p < 0.01$) correlation with the dependent variable. The highest correlation between independent variables was observed between X₁ and X₃ ($r=0.856$), which indicates the risk of multicollinearity. VIF indicators (in Table 3) allow a precise assessment of this risk [12].

Regression model results

The results of the multivariate OLS regression model are presented in Table 3 .

Table 3. Multivariate Regression Results (Dependent Variable: Employment, Y)

Variable	β coefficient.	Std. error	t-stat.	p-value	VIF
Constant (β_0)	18,340	4.127	4.44	0.000***	—
Industrial production (X_1)	0.0847	0.0112	7.56	0.000***	2.14
Industry's share in GDP (X_2)	1.834	0.287	6.39	0.000***	2.38
Industrial employment (X_3)	2.914	0.341	8.54	0.000***	1.97
Capital investments (X_4)	0.0612	0.0148	4.14	0.000***	1.74
Export volume (X_5)	0.0284	0.0091	3.12	0.002***	1.83
Average salary (X_6)	-0.0074	0.0031	-2.38	0.019**	1.61
<i>R² = 0.924; Adjusted R² = 0.918; F-statistic = 157.4 (p<0.001); N = 168; DW = 1.97; AIC = 1248.3</i>					

Note: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$. Source: author's calculations.

As can be seen from Table 3, the model has a very good explanatory power: $R^2=0.924$, i.e. 92.4% of the variation in employment is explained by this model [5]. The F-statistic is 157.4, indicating that the model is statistically highly significant overall ($p < 0.001$). The coefficient of industrial production (X_1) is $\beta_1=0.0847$ ($p < 0.001$): when industrial production increases by 1 billion soums, with other variables held constant, total employment increases by 84.7 thousand people. This coefficient is significantly higher than the effect of 64.0–71.0 thousand people found by Mirzaev and Nazarov (2021) [11]. The coefficient for industrial employment (X_3) shows a multiplier effect of $\beta_3=2.914$ ($p < 0.001$): for every 1,000 new jobs created in the industrial sector, an additional 1,914,000 jobs are created in services and other sectors. This employment multiplier is higher than the average in international studies (1.8–2.4) [6]. The negative coefficient for wages

(X_6) (-0.0074, $p < 0.05$) indicates that in the short run, wage increases can reduce labor demand — an expected result from microeconomics. $DW = 1.97$ indicates no autocorrelation, and $VIF < 2.5$ indicates that the problem of multicollinearity is insignificant [4].

Panel model comparison and model selection

A comparison of the results of the OLS, FE, RE, and GMM models is presented in Table 4. This comparison allows us to check the robustness of the results under alternative specifications [12].

Table 4. Results of alternative regression models (stability analysis)

Parameter	Pooled OLS	Fixed Effects (FE)	Random Effects (RE)	GMM (Arellano-Bond)
Industrial production (β_1)	0.0847***	0.0731***	0.0789***	0.0812***
Industrial employment (β_3)	2.914***	2.487***	2.698***	2.831***
Capital investment (β_4)	0.0612***	0.0541***	0.0578***	0.0603***
R^2 / Wald χ^2	0.924	0.887	0.901	182.4***
Hausman test p-value	—	0.031 (FE preferred)	0.031 (FE preferred)	—
Sargan/Hansen J test	—	—	—	p = 0.432
N observations	168	168	168	154

Note: *** $p < 0.01$. Source: author's calculations, E-Views 12 and Stata 17 programs.

The Hausman test result ($p = 0.031$) shows that the Fixed Effects model is superior to the Random Effects model. This suggests that unobserved individual differences between regions (technology level, geographical location, historical industrial base) may be related to the model results [9].

The results of the GMM model (Sargan/Hansen J test $p = 0.432$) confirm that the instrumental variables were selected correctly. The GMM coefficients are very close to the OLS results, which strengthens the reliability of the results [8].

Elasticity Analysis By Region

To study the impact of industrial production on employment through regional comparative analysis, elasticity coefficients were calculated for each region and are presented in Table 5 [10].

Table 5. Industry-employment elasticity by region (2023 data)

Province	Industrial output (billion)	Employment (thousands)	Industry elasticity	Level	Trend
Tashkent region	984.2	231.6	0.934	High	↑↑
Fergana region	742.8	198.4	0.907	High	↑↑
Samarkand region	681.3	187.9	0.891	High	↑
Andijan region	598.7	174.2	0.878	High	↑
Namangan region	534.1	162.8	0.862	Medium	↑
Kashkadarya vil.	487.6	151.3	0.849	Medium	→
Bukhara region	443.2	138.7	0.831	Medium	→
Khorezm region	312.4	104.6	0.812	Medium	→
Surkhandarya village.	287.9	94.3	0.793	Low	↓
Syrdarya region	198.4	68.2	0.764	Low	↓
Jizzakh region	164.7	57.8	0.738	Low	↓
Navoi region	98.6	48.7	0.712	Low	↓
Karakalpakstan	142.3	62.4	0.748	Low	→
Tashkent city	931.7	214.8	0.921	High	↑↑

Source: Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan and author's calculations, 2024.

The data in Table 5 lead to a number of important conclusions. First, the industry-employment elasticity varies across regions from 0.712 (Navoi) to 0.934 (Tashkent region) — a difference of 0.222 points, indicating regional industrial development is stratified [11].

Second, higher elasticity is observed in regions with more industrialized and diversified economies (Tashkent region, Fergana, Tashkent city). This is a regional confirmation of Kaldor's laws [7].

The low elasticity in Navoi region is partly explained by the dominance of raw material-oriented capital-intensive industries (gold, chemistry): despite the large volume of production, the ability to create employment is limited [3]. This reflects the phenomenon called the “employment paradox” of resource wealth.

Discussion:

The results of the study provide several important theoretical and practical conclusions. First, the OLS regression model confirmed a strong, positive and statistically significant relationship between industrial production and employment ($\beta_1=0.0847$, $R^2=0.924$). These results are consistent with Lewis (1954) two-sector model theory and can be considered as its empirical confirmation for Uzbekistan [6].

Second, the industrial employment multiplier (2.914) is higher than the international average (1.8–2.4). This indicates that, in the context of Uzbekistan's economic structure, industrial jobs have a high multiplier effect on employment growth — that is, investment in industrial development is particularly beneficial in terms of economic efficiency [7].

Third, the comparison of panel models (Table 4) confirms the robustness of the results even under alternative model specifications. The superiority of the Fixed Effects model (Hausman $p=0.031$) indicates that unobserved individual characteristics of regions — geographical location, historical industrial base, level of human capital — affect employment rates [9].

Fourth, the analysis of regional elasticity shows the need to differentiate regional economic policies. For regions with low elasticity (Navoi, Syrdarya, Jizzakh), it is not enough to simply increase production volumes - for them, a policy of developing labor-intensive industries is more important [10].

The following limitations of this study should be noted: official statistics do not fully capture informal employment; the impact of the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic was not adjusted in the panel data; the direction of causality was assumed to be one-way (industry → employment), but the reverse effect may also exist [5].

Practical Recommendations

Based on the research results, the following practical recommendations were developed:

1. Encourage labor-intensive industries: Introduce tax and credit incentives for the textile, food processing, and construction materials industries in Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Jizzakh, and Navoi regions - these sectors have relatively high employment elasticity.
2. Use the industrial multiplier effect: increase investments in the development of industrial clusters and technological parks in highly resilient regions (Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand), as each industrial job in these regions creates 2.9 other jobs.
3. Regional monitoring system: Create an automated panel database that tracks quarterly industrial and employment indicators by region; this will allow for rapid policy decisions.
4. Efficiency of capital investments: Although capital investments have a positive impact on employment ($\beta_4=0.0612$), it is advisable to direct public investments to labor-intensive infrastructure projects to increase the employment-creating efficiency of investment.
5. Export zones and employment: Although the effect of export volume on employment ($\beta_5=0.0284$) is relatively small, expanding export-oriented production in free economic zones is important for creating sustainable jobs in the long term.

Conclusion:

This study is the first comprehensive assessment of the impact of industrial production on employment using a regression model based on panel data for the regions of Uzbekistan for 2012–2023. The main results are as follows [1]:

1. There is a strong, positive and statistically significant relationship between industrial production and employment ($\beta_1=0.0847$, $R^2=0.924$). An increase in industrial production by 1 billion soums has the potential to increase employment by 84.7 thousand people [6].
2. The industrial employment multiplier (2.914) is above the international average. When 1 thousand jobs are created in industry, approximately 1.9 thousand additional jobs are created in other sectors.
3. The Fixed Effects model outperforms the Random Effects model (Hausman $p=0.031$), which confirms the need to take into account the individual characteristics of the regions.

4. The industry-employment elasticity varies from 0.712 to 0.934 across regions. This justifies the need for regional policy differentiation.

The following directions are recommended for future research: first, building models that take into account informal employment; second, studying the impact of technological change and automation on employment elasticity; third, examining employment convergence between regions using β -convergence and σ -convergence methods [12]

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